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Humanitarian Disaster Response: The Impact of Cultural Distance on Bilateral Aid Allocation

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Abstract:

The global climate situation of the last decade remains to be desired. Each year we witness a series of different natural disasters that impact the daily lives of those affected. Due to their Severity, natural disasters sometimes cause considerable damage, exceeding the local government's capacity to respond using their resources but just relying on humanitarian aid. To provide an adequate response, fund allocation from various governments may apply. How does the donor decide whom to help when the need alert comes from all the places in the world, especially if the environment differs from his? Our work aims to study the Hofstede cultural difference of Individualism and Uncertainty Avoidance on the donor's attitude when allocating bilateral funding during natural disaster response from 2014-2019. Using data collected on the FTS website, our result demonstrates a positive attitude of generosity from donors willing to give despite the difference in culture. However, we also notice a change in terms of similarity and non-similarity for high individualism donors when allocating funds, while high Uncertainty avoidance donors demonstrate a static attitude. Our research enables donors to make financial decisions that could improve the flow of donations to better the distant other, which helps to achieve more effective humanitarian aid.

Keywords: Natural hazard, Bilateral Aid, Cultural Distance, Determinant

1. Introduction

In 2015, CRED recorded an increase in natural disasters number, to 376 triggered natural disasters, after the lowest figure since the turn of the century in 2014 (330). According to the World Bank report, the cost of disasters caused by natural hazards to the world economy is 520 billion us dollars per year, pushing 26 million people into poverty each year. Even though most disaster reports do not contain precise economic data, damage estimates for 2014-2017 ranged from a low of \$ 90 billion in 2015 to a high of \$ 340 billion in 2017 (World Bank, 2016).

Every day thousands of individuals go hungry, lack proper housing, or receive inadequate care. Natural disasters, famines, and wars can drag people into situations that no longer allow them to survive independently. These folks have little chance without the assistance of others. Humanitarian aid is one of the responses to the distress caused by the crisis: it saves people, helps them rebuild their lives, and tries to give them hope for the future. It helps alleviate the most severe distress. Facing successive natural disasters, increasing importance is being given to the relief organizations to reduce the impact of disasters on the affected and exposed populations. To accomplish their mission, deployments of financial and in-kind assistance from various sources are part of it.. Even though the budget for global humanitarian aid is constantly rising, there is never enough money. More crises are lasting longer, and humanitarian aid is covering more than it ever has before (OECD, 2017).

The humanitarian financial aid receives increased funds of 1% each year since 2010 (GHO, 2018). However, it observed that some disasters receive more response aid than others; some are "forgotten" or "silent," receiving little or no help from the international community. G. Fink, S. Redaelli, (2009).

Previous researchers have focused on the study of the factors determining the allocation of funds from international agencies and government funds for humanitarian crises to provide solutions. (T.d. Robinson, 2017) for example study on the determinants of the CERF (Central Emergency Response Fund) response during natural disaster; and concluded that several factors are into consideration before being able to proceed with the allocation, that's including (the vulnerability of the recipient's country, the severity caused by the disaster by looking at the number of people affected...). This method is more conducive to major disasters and could easily lead to forgetting and lack of supply for other disasters.

When it's come to bilateral or government funds (Alesina and Dollar, 2000), find that resources are sometimes disproportionately distributed for bilateral aid, depending on political factors, the donor's strategic interest in recipient countries. For instance, according to the author, a donor will prefer to give more to a country with a common language or former colonies.

The majority of the literature on the efficiency of aid also focuses only on the characteristics of recipient countries, which include a variety of economic and social aspects like trade policy, institutions, geography, beginning GDP per capita, etc. Their analysis seems to ignore the intervention aspect of aid delivery. This is crucial when donors are making judgments from societies that are not their own. Due to their dissimilar historical, environmental, economic, and political pasts, Western donors and help recipients from the global South frequently exhibit diverse belief systems and cultures, which shows that the premise of impartiality in aid allocation decisions may not always hold.

Hence, understanding Donor's decisions will help discover the complex nature of real-world donor decision-making, where mechanisms of aid provision assume a crucial role. Distance in humanitarian aid could play a major role in explaining the donor choices. Factors such as cultural distance have been examined in other domains like business Research but have not, to our knowledge, been examined in humanitarian aid. With the increasing demand for financial aid, the influence of cultural distance needs to be considered. This could mean that the greater the difference between a donor and the country of a distant stranger in need, the more difficult it will be for the donor to understand and assess the distant country, which may reduce the probability of donation. This is important because humanitarian aid does not have limited fundraising budgets; unfortunately, donors must make hard decisions on which support and project they should promote. Understanding what the delivery tools and tactics used for decisions are and how it is done has the potential to shed light on donors' Donation intention and development orientation.

In this regard, we are interested in a more neglected aspect, namely the impact of cultural effects on the bilateral government's response to natural disasters.

The main contribution of this paper is the empirical investigation of the role of cultural differences between donors and recipients in the aid-effectiveness.. On the one hand, by adding a measure of assistance efficacy that captures a crucial aspect of the relationship between donors and recipients, this study fills a vacuum in the literature on aid effectiveness. On the other hand, it contributes to the 2016 World Humanitarian Summit, literature on the importance of strengthening the effectiveness of humanitarian aid by studying the effects of cultural differences on aid intervention. The effectiveness of humanitarian aid, of course, is not measured in money alone, and donors are doing more than delivering funds to their humanitarian partners. Understanding the specificities of the contexts in which they work and the population's needs is essential. So is working coherently with others so that donors contribute to collective outcomes beyond humanitarian aid (UN OCHA, 2016).

How do donors decide whom they are going to help? It's a simple question that should draw our attention; in a world, we already face challenges in aid distribution. Bilateral aid is the key element in demonstrating the relationship between the two countries (donor and receiver). It is among the most widely used humanitarian mechanisms when allocating humanitarian funds. However, being in the donor's control is criticized for its character of political-economic interest in giving more to others than those in need. Several believe that there is a link between the cultural impacts in particular (the common language, the same religions...) that influence the donor decision when financing a crisis. (David Stromberg, 2007; Berthelemy, J. C. et al, 2004). For aid effectiveness purposes, in her article Dietrich (2013) shows that bilateral aid is not only provided from government to government but that the latter can, on the contrary, be delivered in different ways, and this, in particular through non-state actors such as NGOs. And according to the author, donors resort to delivery tactics that increase the

likelihood of aid achieving the intended outcome. Therefore, to confirm that, we choose to analyze again on the allocation channel, this time looking at the culture perspective.

It was found during the data collection that the channel in which the fund was distributed differed. It is whether directly from donor countries to recipient countries called as a "direct grant," and the other channel was from the donor country to its own organizations that we named as "intermediate." All of this is going to help build a connection with the donor's cultural dimension. Hence, we ask: By which manner (channel) do donors choose to allocate their funds?

We will be looking at the natural disaster crisis. We selected this crisis because of its impartiality, which means it does not depend on a human decision to happen.

2. Literature Review

Why does a government forgo part of its budget and give it to another country? Why do some countries receive more aid than others? (Schudel C, 2008). These questions have been researched in the past and are still today. Taking an interest in the financing of humanitarian aid cannot be reduced to making an inventory of the sums needed and their destinations. The sources of funding, their origins, the funders' conditions, and the priority allocation choices also carry meaning and crucial issues. The literature on the effectiveness of humanitarian aid is extensive. It presents two types of opposite results: On the one hand, some authors find that according to most of the research published since the late 1990s, international aid has generally been effective, and others have concluded that the aid effectiveness literature has failed to establish that it works (Doucouliago and Paldam, 2005). There is, in particular, Easterly (2005) who lists a "string of failures" by referring to the report on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) presented by the Secretary-General of the United Nations at the United Nations World Summit in September 2005, What are the approaches of this literature which lead to such diverse results?

In studies of the effectiveness of foreign aid, the authors have focused on the conditions under which aid positively impacts growth. The subject was treated according to two main approaches: one which analyzes effectiveness on the recipient countryside and the other analyzes the side of the donor country. We will first review the first approach, which examines what characteristics the recipient country must have to impact positively. The first estimates of aid effectiveness were made using cross-sectional regression with growth as the explanatory variable. According to Headey (2005), cross-sectional regression is not an appropriate method for testing the effects of a wide range of potential determinants of growth. There is, in particular, the problem of the probable endogeneity of aid and especially its propensity to affect growth through several different transmission mechanisms such as levels of investment and consumption, macroeconomic policies, institutions. Also, from Headey's perspective, growth regressions can hardly be used to make statements like "aid was successful." On the other hand, it is possible to say that the aid positively impacted growth under such conditions.

Thus, aid can be effective in "healthy" macroeconomic policy environments (Collier and Dollar, 2002) and in politically stable countries Headey, the argument these authors make is that aid is more likely to be invested than consumed in such environments. Taking the analysis further, (Miquel-Florensa, 2007) explains the result of Collier and Dollar, although controversial, leaves public decision-makers with an open question: what can then be done in countries that have bad policies? How should aid contracts adapt to individual country characteristics to maximize their effectiveness? To answer these questions, the author examines the differential effects between conditional and unconditional aid on growth.

Alesina and Dollar (2000) highlight that donor decision-making regarding foreign aid is more based on political and strategic considerations rather than on the economic needs and political performance of recipient countries. From this perspective, the allocation of aid is therefore perceived as mainly "motivated." Thus, in their article, the two authors put forward a set of results demonstrating this phenomenon. Indeed, they observe that small countries receive more aid than larger ones. More open, democratic countries also tend to receive more aid.

The altruistic suggests that decisions about granting aid should be morally motivated (Silk, J, 2004). Moral motivation means that to the grounds upon which people are actively induced to care for others, to move from benevolence to beneficence. A religious motivation that taught universal solidarity began by helping others less fortunate than oneself and others' love. In this context, it is assumed that donors work in solidarity with beneficiaries to resolve humanitarian crises and fight poverty.

Therefore, tying the motivations for aid to a single underlying cause is an oversimplification of a complex transnational process. To elaborate on this complexity by focusing on aid as an international relation rather than just a financial transaction; Liam Swiss (2017), in his article, analyzes the effect of the global nexus to analyze whether countries with stronger ties or anchoring in the institutions and networks of global society are likely to receive help from more donors. The author used OECD ODA flow statistics to compile a network dataset of all bilateral aid relationships from 1960 to 2008. As a result, those that adhere more closely to and are more integrated into global organizations are the ones who benefit from an increase in aid ties with powerful donor nations.

Focusing on humanitarian aid in the event of natural disasters, which we would expect to have different results due to the independent and natural character of the cause; Wei et al (2016). In their studies, on the direction of donations, for five major earthquakes that occurred between 2008-2012, they show that even with regard to assistance during a natural disaster crisis, the decision to grant aid remains motivated and strongly influenced by politics and economic interests. These were the earthquakes in Wenchuan County in Sichuan Province, China, in 2008, Chile in 2010, Japan in 2010, Haiti in 2010, and eastern Turkey in 2011. These disasters, as said above, had each by their severity, attracted worldwide attention calling for aid.

According to the authors, the effect of gift-giving resulting from aid exchange between donor and recipient; the geographical location of the affected country; the political level (level of corruption and democracy), the commercial opening of each country to the world, the income level of the recipient country could be used as a reason for the fund allocation. Depending on three variables, the fund amount during the disaster, the granting decision if a country has committed to assisting (in cash or in-kind) to countries affected, the donation frequency to count the instances where the granting decision is favorable.

Culture has already been studied as an influencing factor on bilateral trade, FDI, and cross-culture in the workplace Goraieb et al (2019). Studies focusing on culture differ by using many indicators, depending on whether they relate to the impact of culture in the country of destination or that of the cultural distance between the country of origin and the country of destination (Bhardwaj, A et al, 2007) or Whether they use a specific cultural dimension or a composite measure of culture, and whether they include formal institutions as well as the culture in the regression (Schudel C, 2008). However, we observe that fewer studies deal with the impact of culture on aid. A couple of researches have been found discussing the Hofstede dimension culture at the National level and prosocial behavior of the people from those cultures.

Guoq.Liu et al (2018) were trying to find out the prosocial behavior of the people living these cultural dimensions. Find that indulgence verse restraint responds strongly to the three factors, donation, helping, and volunteering. Higher levels of prosocial behavior in a tolerant society can be explained by higher levels of positive emotions from residents of those societies.. People therefore have a great deal of freedom to make decisions and manage their life, and they typically lead happier lives. The negative result of the association between the Long-term Orientation and helping a foreigner was rather strong, this is explained by the fact that the short-term cultural dimension of the society oriented service to others is considered an important objective so that in societies oriented towards the long term and perseverance are considered important goals Hofstede et al (2010).

We also come to literature where that the national culture has an important role during the call to foreign investors; Goraieb et al (2019) analysis proposed that a country with a high level of uncertainty would not invest in the non-similar country of destination because of the unpredictability of the latter in the event. They estimated that High Uncertainty Avoidance in the country of origin should be greater because it is this country that invests and therefore faces greater risks. However, this research's statistical results showed the opposite, the presence of avoidance of high uncertainty in the country of destination as a negative factor for FDI.

Due to the interaction between individuals who establish morals and values that are then externalized by behaviors, culture is both a broad notion and a significant social component. This interaction in our case; explain the collaboration between countries, by looking at how that can assess their impact on humanitarian aid, in other words, to see whether there is a connection between the donor national culture with the amount donated and the donor's preferred allocation chain.

Because it is necessary to know, for a donor State, it is not enough to mobilize consequent financing in favor of the beneficiary; it is also necessary to be able to influence the way in which this financing will be investigated, designed, and above all implemented.

Generally, there are two fund allocation methods, the bilateral (government-to-government channel) and the multilateral (aid from donors is associated with several organizations or institutions). For example, the UN

(United Nations) grouping together several other agencies built on liberal assumptions to promote international cooperation and help states overcome collective action problems (R, Keohane, 2016).

Both chains provide an opportunity for channel selection for the donor because disbursement is done similarly with the same country, the same motivation for aid (Paul A, Raschky, 2012); however, donors still choose to allocate by one of them or both. Our research will focus on the bilateral allocation aid given the connection it establishes between the donor and the aid recipient. The emergence of the more sophisticated presentation of the database collected has allowed us to segment this aid into two parts: direct grant and intermediate grant (when the donor grants the aid through its own organization).

In this study, Hofstede's original research on cultural values in various nations was utilized. He defined four dimensions of cultural values that are present in all nations. For our work, we have selected two dimensions: (1) individualism: explains to what extent the individuals of a society are related to each other or integrated into groups; (2) uncertainty avoidance: affirming a society's tolerance for uncertainty and ambiguity (Hofstede, 1980).

According to St-Arnaud (1995), who describes the intervention model in the psychology of human relations with Hofstede's cultural dimension, it seems that the individualistic aspect, very specific to North American cultures, is part of a perspective of autonomy development. People gradually become more competent at solving their problems, at working themselves on improving their situation or their skills. Therefore, based on the principles of the psychology of human relations, the collaboration of all members concerned by a problem will be sought; the donor will ensure that the initial situation's improvement will be heard.

Once again, this contribution from all the actors suggests that the model is more of a collectivist tendency. Just because ensuring all individuals' participation in improving the initial situation does not mean that the approach is based on collectivist (common) values. On the contrary, it is because of the individual's importance (his needs, interests, ideas, opinions, perceptions, skills) that the approach values his contribution to the process.

Is the culture self-enough to influence or not allocation? We have considered other factors for our research that could influence the donation; they have been mentioned previously in the literature factors such as (geographical distance, corruption, vulnerability). How do the individualist and the UAI donors react to recipients that are distant geographically? How does a country institution-level could influence its decision? Can we resort to the altruistic side of donors by allocating to the most in need and vulnerable?

Currently, the word "vulnerability" is used to describe a condition of weakness, a predisposition to sustain harm, or a limited ability to withstand unfavorable circumstances. It designs both private and public circumstances, moral and material frailties, as well as individuals, objects, and even geographic areas. We selected the per capita GDP and refugees number and economic loss as variables. We assume that a high number of refugees and IDPs combined with low GDP can indicate a history of humanitarian crises in the region and identifies nations with high vulnerability by demonstrating that social services are likely under pressure and have limited capacity to handle additional stress.

The economic loss makes the affected area quite challenging because of a lack of connection to the outside world preventing donors to get much information. In such a situation, most donors will try to get access by the team working on the ground since they get the ease to communicate and coordinate the relief.. Therefore, for reliable indicators concerning how much foreign aid is threatened by aid capture, donors look to the quality of governance in recipient countries when making allocation decisions. The country's institution and government stability, which we measured by using the country corruption index, stipulate that the money should reach the goal of stabilization, however with minor attention have been paid to emergencies aid, bilateral direct grant allocation in the country that has low institutions might face challenges to reach that goal. According to Dietrich in poorly governed recipient countries, donors bypass recipient governments and deliver more aid through non-state actors, else equal. Donors interact with the government and provide more help through the government-to-government channel in recipient nations with better governance.

Therefore, we assume that High Individualism donors by empathy will allocate funds to both having a similar distance in culture, geography. However, the allocation differs for both depending on factors that might be of personal interest. To be sure of the allocation effectiveness, it is strategic to have experience, if possible capitalized and transmitted, to have local expertise, long established in the reality of these beneficiary States. Since its development is done autonomously, this puts them in a position where they have many experiences; and imposes its presence on those non-similar. One of the best ways to impose is to exist on the scene meaning, present on the very ground of the implementation of actions in the beneficiary countries.

Therefore, we Hypothesis:

H1. *High individualism Donors are likely to allocate bilateral disaster assistance to the Distant individualism recipients, by the intermediate channel allocation type.*

On the other hand, in the intervention model, tolerance for ambiguity remains a key concept in articulating the intervention process.

As each intervention has its share of uncertainty, donors must manage and tolerate some ambiguity because of the constant change in the field. The donor must be creative, and above all, must not limit to predefined and restrictive frameworks. Whereas for cultures with strong uncertainty control, change is seen as a threat, a danger. The human relations intervention model, as we have seen, advocates the opposite and has a marked interest in change. In other words, the more there is a difference in culture, the more difficult donation form a high uncertainty avoidance due to lack of confidence in the clarity and planning of events.

Being in High UAI culture, the preference for an indirect bilateral aid allocation does not favor donors. However, in the same perspective of keeping its influence, even its existence in the beneficiary countries, the direct allocation is granted. In this way, the donor is satisfied with the long-distance preservation relationship without involvement in management. Hence the Hypothesis:

H2. *High Uncertainty Avoidance Donors are likely to allocate Bilateral Disaster Assistance by Direct grant channel allocation type to Distant in uncertainty avoidance recipients.*

The possibility that these factors influence the donor decision on the fund and the allocation channel will be demonstrated in the following results. Nevertheless, what about the question of whether the difference in culture affects the amount allocated? This is subject to our third hypothesis.

Already, many studies have shed light on the impact of the humanitarian need of natural disaster measured by the number of deaths, affected, and the choice of the allocation chain in relation to the allocated flow (David Stromger, 2007; G. Fink, S. Redaelli, 2009; T.d. Robinson, 2017). A strong significance linked to the evaluation of its factors in relation to the motivation of the donors revealed differences in the functioning of the participations of the fund allocation.

For example, (Paul A, Raschky, 2010) shows us that in the case of a large disaster, the fatality indicates the humanitarian need and the complexity of the environment in which the donor should operate; hence, this would have an impact on the type of donation and the allocation channel. On the other hand, Wei et al (2016) approve difference in disbursement amount for the wealthy and emerging recipient.

We, therefore, hypothesize that:

H3. *The difference in the culture of individualism and UAI will be significantly associated with the amount allocated in relation to economic loss.*

3. Methodology and date

Our work focuses on determining the allocation of bilateral humanitarian assistance in times of natural disaster. We aim to explain donors' cultural behavior towards recipient countries when allocating funds during natural disasters. In our analysis, we will use a model from the literature in order to target the determinants of humanitarian aid. We used secondary data collected from various sources available online. In this section, we first present our data, then the methodology chosen. we specify the statistical method used, due to our dependent variable's dichotomous nature, we opted for logistic regression for one and Linear regression analysis for the other. These analyzes, as well as all the tests carried out in this research, were done using the statistical software, SPSS version 25. In addition, we have done the moderation analysis of the two cultural values and the economic loss in predicting the bilateral flow.

3.1. Conceptual Framework

In order to further specify the purpose and scope of our approach, additional clarification is required. Our conceptual model for achieving the study's objective is inspired by the natural disaster model designed by (T.d. Robinson, 2017; David Stromberg, 2007) and we bring in a twist by integrating other factors to highlight the interest in our study. As presented in the figure 1, we consider a specific population with a particular vulnerability (GDP, Refugees).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework.

3.2. Dependent and Independent Variables

The bilateral fund amount or Total fund: was obtained from the Financial Tracking Service (FTS) managed by OCHA; it records how much international relief was provided for an individual natural disaster. We collected the income funding from government donors in the same year disaster occurred, by listing from the source (Donor), the destination channel, to the recipient.

The Second Dependent Variable, channel Allocation: Since the FTS lists determined the way or the manner the money was given from the donor to the recipient; we used the dummy variables to illustrate the fund allocation channel, 0: for the direct grant, meaning government to government. One: for intermediate, to explain that fund was given to donor government national organization first, then to recipient's government.

We have considered four independent variables: individualism and uncertainty avoidance, which are the cultural distance that we have considered for our work, then we have the vulnerability, which is composed of the per capita GDP and the refugee number.

3.3. Cultural variables

Cultural differences between countries have always been considered a key influence over how institutions are structured, managed, and on the individual's social behavior within society. As previously cited, culture (religion, common language, colonial ties) was found to influence donor decisions in bilateral aid (David Stromberg, 2007). However, we have decided to use Hofstede's Individualism and uncertainties Avoidance cultural dimensions to test our Hypothesis. Hofstede's model was defined by a system of attitudes, beliefs, and values shared by individuals in a society or group. The difference in the Donor country's culture and the Recipient country were measured by the subtraction of the two values.

Individualism: is a cultural dimension that measures how strong the individuals in a society are tied together or integrated into groups; On individualism, the ties between individuals are loose in the societies; everyone is expected to be relatively independent and self-sufficient. On the other side, there are societies where strong, cohesive, extended families exist, which protect the family members, that is, collectivism.

Uncertainty avoidance: Hofstede defined uncertainty avoidance as a society's tolerance for uncertainty and ambiguity that represents the degree to which individuals of a society try to cope with anxiety by reducing uncertainty (Hofstede, 2010). People in cultures with high UAI scores tend to be risk-averse and generally more sensitive to environmental unpredictability. In societies characterized by a high uncertainty avoidance level, people tend to feel threatened by unfamiliar situations and hardly tolerate ambiguous conditions or deviations from norms. As a result, a strong resistance to change is typical of these societies. A strong avoidance of uncertainty would like to have stable environmental health conditions to avoid risks in their life.

Date or the variables were collected from the Hofstede country comparison site; we took variables from each donor and recipient according to how they scored in the two cultural dimensions.

Refugees: The data incorporate the IDPs, refugees, and stateless persons, encompassing asylum seekers the total number of resident populations of concern within a country. This variable helps to describe pre-disaster vulnerability. Data on refugees and IDPs were acquired from the United Nations High Commissioner's population statistics database for Refugees (UNHCR, 2014).

Gross domestic product per capita: Since the level of economic and social development influences foreign disaster aid to other countries Paul A, Raschky (2010) The recipient country's economic growth is measured here using the GDP per capita, From the world bank database for the year 2014-2019.

Corruption perception Index: Transparency International (2018) defines corruption as the misuse of public power for private benefit. Misuse involves applying illegal and unethical standards. The variable is important; it measures the recipient institution's strength. The donor might like to give to a less corrupt country, knowing that it will benefit more. The data was obtained from the transparency site for the year 2018, with an index from 0, meaning the country is highly corrupted and 100, the government is very clean.

3.4. Controll variables

Beyond the variable of interest, a number of explanatory variables are included in the model. These explanatory variables were taken into account in other research were included as control variables and help avoid variable bias omitted in the estimation technique. We have a geographical distance; as noted in the literature review, there is evidence that neighboring countries are likely to give more due to cultural similarities or diplomatic relations (Wei and Marinova, 2016).

Geographical distance: The geographical distance variable collected here is the distance separating the donor's capital and the recipient in kilometers. The capital data were retrieved from CEP|| (Mayer, T. & Zignago, S. (2011). Although the distance is commonly used as a proxy for bilateral trade, the distance may also capture the relative cost of providing help, especially if aid is provided in kind. It is often the case after natural disasters.

In the case of natural disaster assistance, the number of deaths, the number of people affected, or the economic losses usually measure a country's need. We will focus on disaster fatalities in measuring the economic loss.

Disaster severity: Described by total death, affected, or economic loss, these variables provided by the EM-DAT, have been used to measure the fatality of the disaster. Previous studies emphasize that the higher number of deaths and those affected positively influenced international relief intervention (Wei et al 2019); however, we will focus on the economic loss for our study. It is made up of the current US dollar value of damage to the local economy's infrastructure, crops, and housing. The unit of analysis is the individual country, and all variables are added up through the years 2014–2019.

4. Natural Disaster categories

The natural disaster data were collected from the emergency events database (EM-DAT) maintained by the Center for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED) of the School of Public Health from the Catholic University of Louvain, Brussels, Belgium. CRED defines a disaster as an event bringing together at least one of the following criteria: at least ten people killed; at least 100 people are affected; the government declares a state of emergency or the government requests for international assistance [EM-DAT]. EM-DAT defines six categories of disasters see table 1. For each country, data were acquired for all-natural disasters except the technological disaster category between 2014 and 2019. We collected 398 observations from 21 affected countries.

Table 1. EM-DAT Disaster classifications

Disaster categories	Main types
Geophysical	Earthquake, mass movement (dry), volcano
Meteorological	Cyclone, hurricane, tornado, tropical storm, winter storm
Hydrological	Flood, mass movement (wet)
Climatological	Drought, extreme temperature, fire
Biological	Epidemic
Technological	Industrial accident, transport accident, miscellaneous accident

Source: EM-DAT

We used two dependent variables The First Total amount of the fund (bilateral aid flow) and the fund allocation channel. The total amount or the bilateral humanitarian funding represents the cash donation from donor governments to recipient countries' governments.

5. Analysis and Results

The results of the descriptive statistics highlight from the data collection to the analysis, with more emphasis on the natural disaster and the bilateral fund, by going into more detail on the severity of the disaster (number of people killed and affected) and on the bilateral financial situation. For example, the number of countries financed their characteristics and their geographical location. We collected 398 observations for six types of disasters that occurred in 21 countries between 2014-2019, resulting in the deaths of 926,237 people killed and 1.02 billion people affected, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of the Global Disaster from 2014-2019

Disaster Type	Frequency	Total Death	Total affected	Economic loss
Drought	14	285	32806273	34000
Earthquake	152	836974	531791665	483202000
Epidemic	10	9111	5929003	5191000
Flood	132	44335	317557720	129491934
Storm	83	35455	133880971	309408737
Wildfire	7	77	53361	38850000
Total	398	926237	1022018993	966177671

Source: EM-DAT

The most apparent disaster during these years is the floods, and it also has a large number of the affected; this goes hand in hand with the Cred affirmation of which stipulates that the floods are the type of natural disaster the most frequent (EM-DAT. 2018). The highest disaster mortality was the earthquake; it also has the highest number of economic losses.

Table 3. Regional Fund allocation donor-recipient (in millions of dollars)

	Recipients					
	Asia Pacific	Latin America and Caribbean	Middle East and North Africa	South Pacific	Sub-Saharan Africa	
Asia Pacific	16610715	17182702		7017163	1030388	
Europe and Central Asia	52319204	1479953	11953941	675817	8922047	28147248
Donors Latin America		6987293			6895619	
Middle East and North Africa	153725970	403087			185137	
North America	36250383	458318	10379602	137552	5448160	

^{Note} This illustration was made using UCINET software, where we only wanted to create the network relationship.

SOURCE : Financial Tracking Service

As can be seen in table 3. The region which holds the monopoly of potential donors in North America, where we only find (the USA and Canada).

This also leans in the majority of the report where the two countries are always listed on the top ten. At the same time, we find that the biggest recipient in sub-Saharan Africa, which receives from almost every other region. The vulnerability is due to their geographical location, others due to their economic situation; for

example, low-income countries in these regions are also the most likely to experience natural disasters due to increased vulnerability.

We can also see the table, which goes from the donor to the near region, but only the figure does not show us bilateral donations starting with their own regions. This is a question that we will answer in the next section, which we analyze on geographic distance.

In summary, sharing the same regions does not mean that we automatically share the same culture, the same focus; otherwise, we would not try to understand some of the techniques used by donors when allocating funds.

6. Regression results

What drives the bilateral fund allocation decision from the Donor Perspective? It is a question that has been asked since and got many different answers, and for our work, it is an inevitable question. We will answer it in two phases, as previously said in the first chapter. First, we do the analysis with the bilateral flow (the allocated money as the dependent variable, the result is shown in table 4.

Table 4. the determinant of the bilateral fund allocation

Variables	
Geographical distance	0.008 (0.605)
Refugees	0.069*** (0.000)
GDP per capita	-0.011 (0.439)
Corruption	-0.001 (0.316)
Uncertainty Avoidance	0.001** (0.007)
Individualism	0.001*** (0.000)
Economic loss	0.012*** (0.000)
R ²	137

Note *p<0,05; **p<0,01; ***p<0,001

Based on the findings presented in Table 4, statistical tests revealed that bilateral fund from the donor governments is significantly positive influenced by four named variables: the number of refugees, individualism, uncertainty, and economic loss. Except for the cultural variable, this result demonstrates that the donors look at the disaster impact and the aid beneficiary country's vulnerability. This result goes hand in hand with (Wei and Marinova, 2016; T.d. Robinson, 2017). Tables 5 also show a satisfying value of the variance inflation factors (VIF) to indicate whether an independent variable has a strong linear relationship with the other.

When looking at the cultural distance factors, both results tend to be favorable to allocate funds to the distant culture. Meaning donors with high individualism are likely to donate to the one with a large gap and, at the same time, donors with high uncertainty avoidance respond in the same way. This actually could be interpreted as, despite the difference in culture, when a disaster occurs and has a high impact on an already vulnerable society, donors will respond positively. This brings us back to the concept of altruism; it is out of a good heart that they reacted.

The other variables such as GDP, corruption, and geographic distance have no significant effect.

The second phase is to analyze the channel allocation, how the fund was allocated. We have as variable dependent Channel allocation that we coded as 0: for direct grant, 1: for intermediate. For this analysis, we used logistic regression analyses to bring out the result mentioned in Table 5.

Table 5. Allocation Channel Factors Determinant

Variables	
Geographical Distance	0.000* (0.088)
Refugees	- 0.161 (0.537)
GDP per capita	- 0.152* (0.032)
Corruption	-0.12*** (0.000)
Uncertainty Avoidance	0.126*** (0.000)
Individualism	-0.124*** (0.000)
Economic loss	0.000*** (0.000)
R ²	0.255

Note *p<0,05; **p<0,01; ***p<0,001

The bilateral donation channel results show that most of our values are significant to the channel allocation. The economic loss, Geographical Distance, and uncertainty avoidance show a significantly positive effect. In case where UAI shows a significantly positive ($\beta= 0.126$, $p=0.000$), this indicates that a high score on uncertainty avoidance donor's preference the donation channel through direct Grant, meaning the more different they are with the recipients the more they choose to donate directly. Therefore, H2 is supported.

On the other hand, the variable is such as GDP per capita, corruption, and Individualism are negatively significant. When looking at the individualism value ($\beta= -0.124$, $p=0.000$), Meaning the channel allocation type used by the donor is by intermediate, which also supports the H1. The number of refugees shows a non-significant result.

The moderating effect on the relationship between cultural difference and the amount allocated moderated by the economic loss caused by the natural disaster.

Table 6. IND and UAI interacted with Economic loss in predicting Fund Amount.

Variables	Equation 1	Equation 2
Geographical Distance	0.017(0.242)	0.011(0.444)
Refugees	0.061***(0.000)	0.055***(0.000)
GDP Per capita	0.000(0.93)	0.000(0.878)
Corruption	-0.001(0.171)	-0.001* (0.011)
Uncertainty Avoidance	0.012(0.059)	0.033**(0.001)
Individualism	0.025***(0.000)	0.022***(0.000)
Economic Loss	0.011(0.277)	0.043**(0.005)
Individualism* Economic Loss	0.01(0.439)	
Uncertainty *Economic Loss		0.08**(0.005)
R ²	0.96	0.118

Note *p<0,05; **p<0,01; ***p<0,001

Reading from the first regression equation, the results tell us that there is no significant interaction effect of the control variable and individualism in predicting the amount allocated ($\beta= 0.010$, $p=0.439$). This indicates that Differences in cultural individualism when allocating funds are not influenced by the economic loss. In contrast, the results of the second equation show us a positive significance result of the of the Interaction effect ($\beta= 0.080$, $p=0.005$).

These two results show partial support of the third hypothesis (H3), to have full confirmation of our result; the simple slope analysis is conduct.

Figure 2. Individualism effect on Total Fund Moderated by Economic loss.

Simple slope analysis showed that in high IND donors, no matter the impact of the economic loss caused by the disaster, the similarity in this culture do not imply changes or difference in donation amount. In other words, individualistic donors still donate the same amount to similar cultures. While for the one with low IND culture, the consideration of the economic loss impact applied some variation in the amount allocated. Meaning, the more there is a difference in culture, the more consideration on the Disaster impact before donation.

Figure 3. UAI effect on total fund Moderated by Economic loss.

The simple slope result showed that in high UAI Government, donors donate both to high and low economic loss, which is also demonstrated with the table 4 regression model on the total fund. Since countries with high UAI scores are generally more sensitive to environmental uncertainty, and since this kind of activity usually falls under the service areas of different governmental agencies, it is logical to conclude that these countries might record high donations. Stojcic, I., Kewen, L. Xiaopeng, R. (2016).

From the analysis results obtained, several observations can be highlighted.

The first observation drew results from the analysis of the determinants of aid; as already mentioned, this result showed the altruistic side of donors in the face of major disaster cases, which makes these bilateral donations in times of disaster a particularity by demonstrating human generosity.

The second observation covers the channel through which the aid is distributed; we have discovered that for individualists, the fund channel's disbursement is more done indirectly, which means donors pass through their organizations located or not in the affected area to respond to the crisis. Well, the benefit of this method

is that the donor is involved with all the processes going on in the field and has the possibility to give instructions and request reports.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study explored the impact of cultural differences on the attitude of the donor in the allocation of bilateral aid during natural disasters. According to our results, the cultural distance would have little impact on the attitude of the donor, whether individualist or Uncertainty Avoidance. More so, this study points out that it would also influence the mode of fund allocation. This research brings new knowledge on the issue of the determinant of bilateral aid, given the few studies on natural disasters, humanitarian aid, and the notion of cultural differences from the angle of Hofstede's cultural dimensions. It also provides interesting information on the notion of understanding donation preferences between donor and recipient and establishes another track of the relationship between the two. In addition, we understand that cultures differ from each other, which makes the world a wonderful place filled with diversity. However, our work is not about showing which of the two is better than the other, but it allows us to discover and accept these differences.

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